

RESPONSIBLE SOURCING OF BUILDING MATERIALS: FROM DUE DILIGENCE TO MARKET UPTAKE.

ABOUT

In this field note, we share findings from a workshop held at the Sustainable Buildings and Construction Summit in Lausanne, 22 April 2026. The session, *Responsible Sourcing of Construction Materials: Bridging Due Diligence and Market Uptake*, was co-hosted by the Concrete Sustainability Council and the Coalition for Responsible Sand and Silicates. Organisations in the room included Bellona Europa, TU Delft, Green Building Alliance, Holcim, Architecture 2030, American Wood Council, EBRD, Penn State, WWF.

In this summary, we capture what we heard from a knowledgeable group of participants in a session that was shorter than planned. It is not a consensus document. Where we describe a view, it may come from one voice or a few. We present these as signals worth following, not conclusions. A wholehearted thank you to our panellists: Marco Sirotti (Bellona Europa), Eugenia Ceballos (Holcim), Marc Goichot (WWF), Geneviève Sherman (Concrete Transition Capital) and Cynthia Imesch (CSC).

BACKGROUND: THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR AS DEMAND DRIVER FOR CONCRETE AND AGGREGATES

The built environment is the dominant market for sand, gravel, crushed stone and the broader silicate mineral family. It is the market. The demand signal. Over 40 billion tonnes of aggregates are consumed annually for construction, making these the most extracted solid materials on Earth.

Aggregates make up 60 to 75 per cent of concrete by volume. Construction accounts for 70 to 80 per cent of global flat glass demand. Solar glass, ceramic tiles, sanitaryware, dimension stone, fibre optic cabling and semiconductor chips all depend on sand and silicate minerals. These materials are not just in the foundations, structures and fittings in of our buildings. They are in the intelligence we're embedding in smart buildings, too. And every specification, every tender, every project shapes the conditions under which these materials are extracted around the world.

WHY THIS CONVERSATION MATTERS

Before the structured discussion began, a globally recognised expert in concrete innovation asked to speak. They come from a place where sand mining is largely uncontrolled. They described how their village has been transformed by extraction feeding demand in the capital city. Roads degraded and dangerous. Lives lost. Criminal elements involved. Rivers and landscapes unrecognisable. They reflected on their professional world, working on the technical frontiers of concrete innovation, and said they often think: "But what about the sand? Why aren't we talking about this too?"

The 40 billion tonnes GAIN estimates are produced and consumed each year are not an abstraction. Every grain, granule and stone comes from somewhere, and the conditions under which they are extracted have consequences for real communities.

WHAT COUNTS AS RESPONSIBLE SOURCING IN THE SECTOR?

The session found broad recognition that responsible sourcing of construction materials is currently fragmented. Companies are trying to manage risks and make progress, but without shared language or a coordinated framework. Two approaches seem to coexist. Individual companies undertake proactive sustainable procurement guided by their own policies and enabled by sustainability certifications (the CSC model). The OECD Due Diligence Guidance (2016) on responsible minerals supply chains is risk-based. It asks do we understand our supply chains more broadly and have a process for identifying and responding to risks in them.

An experienced voice in sustainable procurement suggested best practice is a blend of both. They also reflected that their approach has become risk-based by default, because the volumes and number of sites involved make anything else impractical: "I choose my battles carefully. If local laws are sound, I ask for paper-based reporting. If not, I visit the site." They observed it would be genuinely useful to have extended guidance on due diligence for construction materials, building on the recently published OECD work on sand and silicate supply chains (OECD 2026) as the EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive enters into force.

CARBON, CO-BENEFITS AND THE ATTENTION PROBLEM

The CO₂ intensity of cement production at the processing stage draws the overwhelming share of attention, meaning that upstream extraction risks like impacts on biodiversity, water systems, human rights are being overlooked. An urban planning expert offered a reframe: rather than treating upstream impacts as competing with carbon, there are significant co-benefits. Responsible sourcing at the extraction end can contribute to carbon reduction, supply security, ecosystem resilience and social outcomes simultaneously. Working with these co-benefits could integrate upstream due diligence into the sector's existing carbon agenda.

ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY SOLUTIONS MUST FOCUS ON VALUE FOR UPTAKE

Scaling circular economy approaches is critical to reducing virgin demand, but current mechanisms need calibration. Waste reuse targets can create perverse incentives, encouraging waste generation or long-distance transport. Quality concerns around recycled aggregates were treated as manageable if materials are matched to appropriate applications. The CSC already includes an add-on module rewarding recycled concrete use. Participants emphasised that making responsible materials cheaper than virgin sources is a key opportunity, and that value creation, not just compliance, must underpin all efforts to see these materials and approaches go mainstream.

SAND AND CONCRETE ARE INTERCONNECTED WITH RESILIENCE LOSSES AND GAINS

Sand and gravel in their natural state are functional components of living systems. They are the riverbeds and shape their course. They are the coastline and also protect it. They filter and store groundwater. They are and support habitats. When extracted at scale without reference to what those systems can sustain, the result is a measurable loss of resilience.

The conversation surfaced this as a two-sided relationship. The construction sector's demand for sand and aggregates can undermine the climate resilience of the environments from which it sources. But the concrete and built infrastructure that these materials become is itself a resilience asset, protecting communities and enabling recovery after disaster. The same material flow that erodes resilience when extraction is poorly managed can build resilience if produced and used responsibly.

This duality makes responsible sourcing of sand and aggregates fundamentally a resilience question. The concept of sand budgets, raised during the session, speaks directly to this: understanding how much material a system can sustainably yield is a prerequisite for ensuring that the resilience we build with concrete is not purchased at the cost of resilience lost at the source. And this one factor that makes responsible sourcing and use of these materials very context specific.

ENABLING CONDITIONS

Participants identified conditions needed to support responsible sourcing of construction materials:

- **Shared foundations.** Value chain alignment on expectations and processes. Trust between actors who have not historically worked together. Sensible design of requirements.

- **Practical infrastructure.** Reliable supply chain data. Traceability systems and digital passports at scale. Harmonised methodologies. Transparency as a norm.
- **Market and regulatory signals.** Integration into green building certifications, public procurement and sustainable finance. Alignment with the European Taxonomy. Cost-competitive responsible materials. Proportionate compliance costs, with lessons from smallholder certification in timber and agriculture.
- **Capacity.** Value chain education. Knowledge of financial instruments. Practical implementation. Credible claims and frameworks.

WHERE THIS POINTS

Four recommended directions emerged in the conversation:

1. **Sector-specific due diligence guidance.** Exploring whether the OECD sand and silicate supply chain work could be extended to broader construction materials flows, meeting a growing need as the CSDDD takes effect.
2. **A joint working group.** The Coalition and CSC are exploring a working group bringing together willing actors to shape practical guidance grounded in sector realities. We welcome expressions of interest.
3. **Strengthening existing certification.** CSC will explore what can be done within its framework to strengthen recognition of responsible aggregate sourcing for concrete.
4. **Learning from other sectors.** The timber sector offers a precedent: 70 per cent of mills are now third-party verified, and initial cost concerns faded with time. A structured lessons-learning exercise could yield practical insights for construction materials.

These are starting points, not finished plans.

We welcome further conversation.

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SUGGESTED CITATION

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